

Building Resilient Economies Amid Insecurity: Informal Governance and Livelihoods in Rural Communities in Okene and Kabba-Bunu Local Government Areas, North Central Nigeria

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Abstract

Rural communities in conflict-affected areas often develop adaptive mechanisms to sustain livelihoods in the absence of effective state institutions. This study examines how informal governance and social capital shape livelihood strategies in selected communities in Okene Local Government Area (Kogi Central) and Kabba-Bunu Local Government Area (Kogi West) in North Central Nigeria. Specifically, the study explores the emergence of informal governance systems, the role of social capital in livelihood adaptation, and whether these adaptive strategies contribute to economic development. A qualitative research design was adopted, using in-depth interviews and focus group discussions with 33 purposively selected participants, including farmers, community leaders, women traders, and informal security actors. Data were analyzed using a deductive thematic approach informed by Social Capital Theory and Diffusion of Innovations Theory. Findings indicate that hybrid security arrangements fill governance gaps and support livelihood adaptation through collective farming, diversification, and information sharing. However, these strategies primarily sustain short-term resilience rather than promote long-term economic development. Structural constraints, including insecurity, exclusion from decision-making, and limited market access, hinder the transition from coping to growth. The findings are context-specific to the study areas but may offer insights for similar conflict-affected rural settings. The study recommends integrating informal and formal governance systems and strengthening inclusive, development-oriented interventions to support sustainable economic growth.

Keywords: Informal governance, social capital, livelihood adaptation, insecurity, rural development.

Introduction

In many rural communities within Okene and Kabba-Bunu Local Government Areas of North Central Nigeria, insecurity has increasingly disrupted agricultural production and livelihood systems. Persistent farmer–herder conflicts, banditry, and communal violence have contributed to declining productivity, displacement, and food insecurity (Silas et al., 2023; International Crisis Group, 2020). These conditions pose significant challenges to sustainable economic development in rural areas.

From a theoretical and policy perspective, the state is expected to provide security, protect property rights, and facilitate market access—conditions necessary for economic growth (Murtazashvili & Murtazashvili, 2021). However, in many rural areas, the limited presence of formal institutions has led communities to rely on informal governance systems, including traditional authorities and vigilante groups, to maintain order and coordinate economic activities (Ojewale, 2023; Kehinde et al., 2024).

In fragile contexts, such arrangements are often described as hybrid governance systems, which emerge organically to fill institutional gaps rather than as deliberate policy constructs (Bagayoko et al., 2016). While these systems can enhance local stability and reduce transaction costs, they do not necessarily promote long-term economic development and may, in some cases, reinforce exclusion or limit formal economic integration (Hakeem & Musa, 2025; Nda-Yakubu, 2025).

At the household level, insecurity has driven livelihood adaptation strategies, including collective farming, relocation to safer areas, and diversification into non-farm activities (Onuwa et al., 2022; Adisa et al., 2022). Although these strategies enhance survival, they are often defensive in nature and may not lead to sustained improvements in productivity or income.

The effectiveness of these adaptive strategies is closely linked to social capital, which encompasses the networks, trust, and norms that facilitate cooperation within communities (Woolcock, 2016). Social capital can support resilience by enabling access to resources and information, particularly through kinship ties, cooperatives, and religious organizations (Morshed et al., 2023). However, strong bonding networks may also reinforce inequality and exclusion, especially for marginalized groups such as women, youth, and migrants (Rjoub et al., 2021; Pena-López et al., 2021).

Despite the growing body of literature on conflict, informal governance, and livelihood adaptation, these areas are often studied in isolation. As a result, there is limited understanding of how informal governance and social capital interact to shape both short-term resilience and long-term economic development, particularly in rural, conflict-affected settings.

This study distinguishes between three related but conceptually distinct ideas. Resilience refers to the capacity of communities to absorb shocks while maintaining basic livelihood functions. Coping strategies are short-term adaptive responses to crisis conditions. In contrast, economic development involves sustained improvements in productivity, income, and market integration. While resilience and coping are critical for survival, they do not necessarily translate into development outcomes. Against this background, the purpose of this study is to examine how informal governance and social capital interact to shape

livelihood adaptation and influence economic outcomes in selected communities in Okene and Kabba-Bunu Local Government Areas. Specifically, the study seeks to:

1. Examine the emergence and functioning of informal governance systems in areas with weak state presence;
2. Assess the role of social capital in supporting livelihood adaptation under conditions of insecurity;
3. Determine whether adaptive strategies contribute to economic development or primarily sustain coping and resilience.

This study provides context-specific insights and does not seek to generalize beyond the study areas, although the findings may offer useful implications for similar conflict-affected rural contexts.

Research Questions

The study is guided by the following research questions:

1. How do informal governance systems emerge and function in areas with limited state presence?
2. What role does social capital play in shaping livelihood adaptation under conditions of insecurity?
3. To what extent do these adaptive strategies contribute to economic development, as opposed to sustaining short-term coping and resilience?

Theoretical Framework

This study draws on Social Capital Theory and Diffusion of Innovations Theory.

Social Capital Theory explains how networks and relationships facilitate access to resources and support. Bonding capital supports internal cooperation, bridging capital enables access to new opportunities, and linking capital connects communities to formal institutions.

Diffusion of Innovations Theory explains how new practices spread through social networks. In this context, adaptive strategies—such as collective farming or security arrangements—are transmitted through trusted social relationships.

Together, these theories provide a framework for understanding how communities adapt to insecurity and how such adaptations influence economic outcomes.

Research Method

This study employed a qualitative research design in selected communities in Okene and Kabba-Bunu Local Government Areas of North Central Nigeria. A total of 33 participants were purposively selected, including farmers, community leaders, women traders, and informal security actors. Snowball sampling was

subsequently used to recruit additional participants, and sampling continued until data saturation was achieved.

Data were collected through two focus group discussions and multiple in-depth interviews, each lasting approximately 40–50 minutes and conducted in private settings. All participants provided informed consent, and measures were taken to ensure confidentiality and anonymity. Given the sensitive nature of the study context, the research adhered to the “do no harm” principle.

Data were analyzed using a deductive thematic approach guided by the study’s theoretical framework. Transcripts were independently coded by two researchers, and emerging themes were identified and refined through comparison and consensus.

Results and Discussion

The findings presented here reflect the experiences of participants in selected communities in Okene and Kabba-Bunu Local Government Areas. The analysis is organized into key themes emerging from the data.

Emergence of Informal Governance

Participants consistently reported the emergence of informal security arrangements due to the limited presence of formal state institutions. Community-based vigilante groups and traditional leadership structures were identified as central to maintaining order.

A community leader explained:

“We could not wait for the government anymore. We organized ourselves to protect our people and our farms.”

Similarly, a farmer noted:

“Without the vigilante group, many of us would have stopped going to the farm completely.”

While these systems enhanced local security, some participants raised concerns about accountability and informal levies imposed on community members.

Livelihood Adaptation Strategies

In response to insecurity, participants described significant adjustments in their livelihood practices. Many reported shifting to smaller or safer farmlands, engaging in collective farming, and diversifying into non-agricultural activities.

A participant stated:

“We now farm in groups so that we can watch out for each other.”

Women participants highlighted increased involvement in petty trading:

“Farming is no longer reliable, so we sell food items and other small goods to survive.”

These strategies were primarily aimed at reducing risk rather than increasing productivity.

Role of Social Capital

Social networks played a critical role in facilitating adaptation. Participants emphasized the importance of trust, kinship ties, and community associations in sharing information and resources.

One respondent noted:

“Information spreads quickly through our groups. If there is danger somewhere, everyone knows.”

Another added:

“We depend on each other now more than before. Without that, survival would be difficult.”

Mobile phones were also identified as important tools for communication and coordination.

Constraints and Social Exclusion

Despite the benefits of social capital, access to resources and decision-making was not evenly distributed. Women, youth, and migrants reported limited participation in governance structures.

A female participant explained:

“Men are the ones making decisions. We are mostly informed after.”

Additionally, some participants expressed fatigue with prolonged reliance on collective coping mechanisms:

“People are getting tired. Everyone is struggling, and there is little support.”

Discussion of Findings

Although the importance of informal governance and social capital in building resilience in conflict-affected settings has been widely acknowledged, their connection to economic development remains insufficiently explored. This study examined this relationship in selected rural communities in Okene and Kabba-Bunu Local Government Areas of North Central Nigeria. The findings indicate that while informal governance

structures are effective in supporting survival and stabilizing local livelihoods, they do not necessarily translate into sustained economic development.

A substantial majority of participants (84.8%) expressed appreciation for the benefits of hybrid security arrangements within their communities. Vigilante groups and traditional council systems were widely perceived as filling critical governance gaps left by limited state presence. This finding confirms the existence of hybrid governance structures as described in the literature (Bagayoko et al., 2016; Ojewale, 2023). The legitimacy of these arrangements appears to be rooted not in formal authority but in their effectiveness in maintaining order and enabling economic activities, such as night trading and the timely resolution of land disputes. This supports the argument by Murtazashvili and Murtazashvili (2021) that property protection and market access are fundamental to economic activity, and that communities will rely on informal mechanisms where formal state provisioning is weak.

In response to insecurity, a large proportion of respondents (75.8%) reported shifting to smaller, safer farmlands and adopting collective farming practices. Additionally, all female participants indicated engagement in livelihood diversification through vending or small-scale retailing. These findings are consistent with Adisa et al. (2022) and Onuwa et al. (2022), who identify collective farming and diversification as common adaptive strategies in response to farmer–herder conflicts in Nigeria. However, these adaptations appear to be largely defensive rather than transformative. A notable proportion of respondents (42.4%) reported no improvement in productivity, while 27.3% experienced a decline in income despite diversification efforts. This aligns with Mabe (2024), who argues that livelihood adaptations in insecure environments tend to sustain subsistence rather than promote economic expansion.

The study further found that coping strategies spread rapidly through social networks. Nearly all participants (90.9%) reported adopting at least one coping mechanism through kinship or cooperative networks, while 57.6% identified mobile phones as an important tool for information sharing and early warning. These findings support the relevance of Diffusion of Innovations Theory (Rogers, 2003) in conflict-affected rural contexts, where trusted social networks facilitate the rapid transmission of risk-reducing practices. However, consistent with the theory, the rate of adoption varied by type of innovation. Productivity-enhancing innovations, such as improved seeds, were adopted by only 30.3% of participants, whereas survival-oriented strategies diffused more widely. This suggests that persistent insecurity may suppress risk-taking behavior necessary for development-oriented innovation, an issue that remains underexplored in the livelihood adaptation literature (Justino, 2023).

Despite the benefits of social capital, access to networks and resources was uneven. Women (75.0%), youth (54.5%), and migrant residents (66.7%) reported exclusion from key decision-making and resource-sharing structures. In addition, nearly half of the participants (48.5%) reported experiencing social fatigue, indicating limits to prolonged reliance on community-based coping mechanisms. These findings reinforce the argument by Rjoub et al. (2021) that strong bonding social capital can deepen internal hierarchies and inequality in polarized settings. Similarly, Pena-López et al. (2021) highlight how unequal access to social networks constrains economic mobility in marginalized communities. The predominance of bonding over

bridging and linking social capital in the study areas, as also observed by Woolcock (2016), likely restricts access to external markets, institutional support, and new economic opportunities, thereby constraining long-term growth.

This study is not without limitations. It was conducted over a three-week period within a limited geographic scope and therefore does not claim representativeness beyond the selected communities in Okene and Kabba-Bunu Local Government Areas. The use of snowball sampling may have limited the inclusion of the most marginalized groups, and recall bias may have influenced some responses.

Overall, the findings suggest that while informal governance and social capital are critical for sustaining livelihoods under conditions of insecurity, they may inadvertently reinforce subsistence conditions and hinder pathways to economic development. This underscores the need for clearer distinctions between interventions aimed at supporting short-term coping and those designed to promote long-term, inclusive economic growth in conflict-affected rural communities.

Conclusion

This study examined how informal governance and social capital shape livelihood adaptation in conflict-affected communities in Okene and Kabba-Bunu, North Central Nigeria. Findings show that hybrid governance and social networks support coordination, collective action, and short-term resilience in the face of weak state presence and insecurity.

However, these strategies are largely defensive and subsistence-oriented, limiting their contribution to sustained economic growth. Structural barriers—such as poor market integration, low adoption of productivity-enhancing innovations, and the exclusion of women, youth, and migrants—constrain long-term development. As such, resilience reflects survival rather than meaningful economic advancement.

The study highlights the need to distinguish between coping, resilience, and development. While informal systems are vital in crisis contexts, they must be integrated with formal institutions to promote inclusive and sustainable growth. Strengthening market access, expanding productive resources, and ensuring inclusive participation are critical. Future research should explore the long-term economic impacts of these adaptive strategies and the conditions under which resilience can translate into development.

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